

POMEGRANATE IS A BERRY OR FRUI

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Annotation: There is confusion in the classification of the pomegranate. People are wondering whether a pomegranate is a fruit or a berry, because they heard somewhere that a pomegranate is a berry, but in everyday life it is considered that it is a fruit.

Culinary. In fact, there are two classifications by which a pomegranate can be identified. According to the first classification, culinary and household, pomegranate, of course, is a fruit. Because the pomegranate fruit is sweet in taste, and the main feature of the fruit is that it is sweet and juicy.

Key words: Citrus fruits, storage, temperature, humidity, initial quality, storage.

Botanical. The second classification is botanical. In botany, there is no term "fruit". The word "fruit" is used here. The fruit is the part of the plant that develops from the flower and contains the seeds. The fruits are also divided into different types. Pomegranate refers to juicy fruits, which, in turn, are divided into berry-like. Pomegranates are a variety of berries, and their fruit is called pomegranate. Also a variety of berries is a berry, which includes banana, currant

and tomato.

Outcome. Therefore, it is not entirely correct to call pomegranate fruits berries, they are a type of berry, but not a berry. And the very definition of berries sounds like this, berries are juicy, with a thin peel and multi-seeded fruits of plants. Although, for simplification, you can call pomegranate fruits and berries.

Useful properties of pomegranate seeds have been known for a long time. Pomegranate juice was widely used for healing purposes by ancient healers. Pomegranate is a symbol of fertility, a female fruit that has a number of very useful qualities. Thanks to the vitamins and microelements contained in pomegranate juice, this drink not only strengthens the body's immune system and is an excellent prevention of various diseases, but its regular use helps to cure some ailments.

Amino acids, citric and other organic acids are found in large quantities; also included in the pomegranate folacin, tannin, pectin, iron, potassium, calcium.

Pomegranate juice is an excellent diuretic and antiseptic, has an anti-inflammatory effect, is easily absorbed by the body and is not contraindicated even for diabetics.

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